

ISic3562

I.Sicily inscription 3562

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance

contrada Benesiti, casual find

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337255

1. [— —]A v̄ EIΔEKV vacat
2. [— —]N v̄ ΓΓNH vacat
3. [— —]. N ²⁷[—]M(?)²⁷ v̄ ΩMΓ vacat
4. [— —]ΣK v̄ ΣΣ' ΤΟΣ vacat
5. [— —]ΟΝΟΣΠΙΟΚΑΙ
6. [— —]ΧΣΟΡΟΦΑΝΕ
7. [— —]ΚΛΕΗ v̄ ΤΟΣΑΝΕ [—?—]
8. [— —]Α v̄ Σ vacat
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645636

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0930

Distefano, S. 2002. Il Palmento di Acremonte. Contributo alla storia dei vini dell'ager Acrensis tra Tardo Antico e Medioevo. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 89-112. At 102 n.54, 100 fig.12, 106 no.11

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